

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING TASK-BASED LANGUAGE LEARNING APPROACH IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Bektosheva Durdonakhon Bakhtiyorovna

**Assistant English instructor of the department: Pedagogy, psychology, and foreign
 languages, Nukus Innovation Institute**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10939746>

Abstract. This article presents the role of the Task-Based Language Learning (TBLL) approach in modern English language education. TBLL is known for its emphasis on real-world tasks as a medium for language acquisition, advocating for a shift towards communicative competence and practical application over mere theoretical knowledge. Through the application of TBLL, English is not just taught as a subject, but experienced as a living, breathing mode of communication, reflecting its global use and applicability.

Keywords: Task-Based Language Learning, English language teaching, communicative competence, real-world tasks, learner motivation.

Introduction. The article sets the stage by positioning TBLL against the backdrop of evolving pedagogical paradigms in English language teaching. It highlights the transition from traditional grammar and translation methods to approaches that prioritize communication and practical language use. TBLL is framed as a response to the global demand for English language proficiency in diverse communicative contexts.

The Task-Based Language Learning (TBLL) approach, also known as Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), has gained significant recognition in the field of language education, particularly in teaching English [5]. This approach prioritizes the use of authentic language through meaningful tasks, reflecting real-life situations that learners might encounter outside the classroom. The importance of TBLL in teaching English can be highlighted through several key aspects:

TBLL emphasizes the use of language for genuine communication, preparing students to use English in real-world situations. This approach helps learners develop their ability to express themselves in diverse contexts, enhancing both fluency and accuracy.

By engaging learners in tasks that have clear, practical objectives, TBLL can significantly boost motivation. When students see the direct application of their language skills to fulfilling meaningful goals, their engagement and enthusiasm for learning tend to increase [2].

Tasks in TBLL often require learners to solve problems or complete projects collaboratively. This not only improves their language skills but also fosters critical thinking, creativity, and teamwork—skills valuable beyond the language learning classroom.

TBLL situates language learning within authentic contexts, making the learning process more relevant and memorable. Using real-life materials and scenarios aids in the natural acquisition of language, mirroring how native speakers learn their first language.

Rather than isolating language skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing), TBLL encourages the integration of all four. Tasks are designed to require multiple skills, reflecting the multifaceted nature of real-world language use [4].

Tasks can be adapted to suit the interests, needs, and proficiency levels of different learners. This personalization supports more effective learning, as students are more likely to engage with content that resonates with their experiences and goals.

TBLL often incorporates a reflective phase, where learners evaluate their performance and strategies. This reflection encourages deeper learning and self-awareness as language users. Performance-based assessment in TBLL provides a more holistic view of a learner's language abilities than traditional testing. Observing students as they complete tasks offers insights into their practical language use, not just their theoretical knowledge.

This approach aligns with theories of second language acquisition that emphasize the importance of meaningful communication in learning. Engaging in tasks mimics the natural language acquisition processes, where comprehension and production are developed through interaction [1].

By exposing learners to a variety of tasks and contexts, TBLL prepares them for the unpredictability and diversity of real-life language use, equipping them with the skills to navigate new language situations confidently.

As it is known that the Task-Based Language Learning approach offers a dynamic and effective strategy for teaching English, addressing the practical, communicative, and interactive dimensions of language learning. It prepares learners not just to know about the English language but to use it competently in their personal, academic, and professional lives.

Conclusion. TBLL represents a paradigm shift in English language teaching, emphasizing the importance of practical language use and communicative competence. By focusing on tasks that mimic real-life scenarios, TBLL not only enhances motivation and engagement but also prepares learners for the complexities of global communication. Its emphasis on personalized, reflective, and integrated learning makes TBLL a critical approach in developing proficient, confident English language users for the 21st century.

References:

1. Bhandari, L. P. (2020). Task-based language teaching: A current EFL approach. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 11(1), 1-5.
2. Calvert, M., & Sheen, Y. (2015). Task-based language learning and teaching: An action-research study. *Language Teaching Research*, 19(2), 226-244.
3. Izadpanah, S. (2010). A study on task-based language teaching: From theory to practice. *US-China Foreign Language*, 8(3), 47-56.
4. Thomas, M. (2013). Task-based language teaching and CALL. *Contemporary computer-assisted language learning*, 341-358.
5. Van den Branden, K. (2016). The role of teachers in task-based language education. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 36, 164-181.